

Lewis acid zeolite catalysts *via* chemical modification of extra-large pore germanosilicates

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ABSTRACT

Lewis acid zeolites containing tetravalent metals, such as Sn or Zr, are of great interest as catalysts for various reactions owing to their tunability, activity, and reusability. In the context of emerging trends in biomass-related substrates processing, the synthesis of Lewis acid zeolites with extra-large pores presents a key step by addressing diffusion restriction associated with these molecules. In this paper, we report on the incorporation of Sn and Zr into extra-large pore zeolites UTL and *CTH through a four-step approach, including synthesis of parent germanosilicate zeolites, followed by their post-synthesis stabilization, degermanation, and metal incorporation. The resulting zeolites were examined in Meerwein–Ponndorf–Verley (MPV) reduction of furfural in batch and flow reactors. In a batch, the designed Lewis acid extra-large pore zeolites exhibited similar yields to the MPV reduction product as the respective Sn- and Zr-substituted zeolite *BEA known as the optimum catalysts for this reaction. On the other hand, a better mass balance was observed for the MPV reduction of furfural over UTL/Sn (91%) vs. *BEA/Sn zeolite catalysts (73 – 91%) in a batch mode, suggesting the hindered formation of insoluble furfural transformation products in the extra-large pore system of UTL zeolite. Showing stable performance in MPV reduction in a flow reactor (50% selectivity to MPV reduction product at 20 – 25% furfural conversion), the extra-large pore Sn-UTL zeolite designed in this study was verified as a promising solid Lewis acid catalyst under industrially relevant conditions.

1. Introduction

Metallosilicate zeolites that possess active sites related to M(IV) atoms in a formal oxidation state +4 (M = Ti, Sn, Zr) are of great interest as catalysts for the upgrading of biomass and the synthesis of specialty chemicals [1,2]. The catalytic performance of such materials is closely associated with the nature of coordinatively unsaturated metal sites incorporated into the silica matrix. Titanosilicate zeolites emerged as active and selective catalysts for the epoxidation of alkenes and the hydroxylation of aromatics [3–5], while Sn-zeolites demonstrated outstanding performance in the Baeyer–Villiger oxidation of aldehydes and ketones [6–8], and the isomerization of sugars [9]. Furthermore, Sn- and Zr-zeolites have been found to be highly active catalysts in MPV reduction of biomass-derived aromatic aldehydes [10–13]. When considering a typical size of biomass-derived molecules, the access of the reagents to the active sites is one of the key targets in the design of

appropriate catalysts [14–16]. In general, the access of the reacting molecules to active sites in zeolites can be tuned by manipulating their crystal morphology or pore system [17] without altering their topology. However, intrinsic micropore openings continue to represent bottlenecks for the effective diffusion of the reacting molecules and their interaction with the active sites in any case. Most reported M(IV)-zeolites are confined to large pore (12-ring) matrixes, sometimes leading to severe diffusion constraints, particularly when bulky molecules are involved [18]. Recently, Liu et al. described the synthesis of Sn-*CTH, which is an extra-large pore (14-ring) zeolite, with varying Si/Sn ratios using an acid-hydrolysis process [19]. However, the authors observed the presence of extra-framework tin for Si/Sn ratios surpassing the theoretical value of 50, highlighting the constraints of their approach in successfully integrating a substantial amount of tin into the *CTH structure through post-synthetic methods.

Accordingly, the imperative is to design extra-large pore (≥ 14 -rings)

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stanno / zirconosilicate zeolites with novel topologies. The majority of extra-large pore zeolites are germanosilicates, usually with a low Si/Ge ratio (less than 10) in the framework [20,21]. Germanosilicate zeolites are commonly characterized by high pore volumes (up to 40% of total zeolite volume) and low framework densities (up to 10.5 T/1000 Å³), making them highly promising candidates for design of catalysts efficiently converting bulky molecules [20].

Despite their attractive structural features, germanosilicate zeolites are rarely considered as targeted catalysts because of their structural instability in the presence of moisture and weak acidity [22]. Although such zeolites have been reported to catalyze diverse processes, the structural degradation of germanosilicates inevitably took place during these catalytic reactions [23–25]. Structural changes occur when Ge is uncontrollably leached from calcined (organic structure-directing agent (OSDA)-free) Ge-rich zeolites [26,27]. In certain cases, germanosilicates may even undergo immediate collapse after OSDA removal [22]. In fact, an increase in the micropore size is usually accompanied by a decrease in stability. For example, while large-pore IWW zeolite showed maintenance of the structure [28], extra-large pore UTL and *CTH decomposed during aqueous or acidic treatment [26,27,29].

In turn, partial post-synthesis Ge-for-Si substitution by treating UTL zeolites with a silica source in ethanolic acid solutions or *CTH zeolites with concentrated acid solution allowed the preparation of stabilized Ge-poor extra-large pore zeolites [23,30]. Wu [31] and Tuel *et al.* [32] reported a stabilization method by treating the as-prepared zeolite with concentrated acid solution. The stabilized materials possess high Si/Ge ratios (≥ 44), which, however, provided a limited number of potential positions for the incorporation of heteroatoms [33,34], limiting the performance of the resulting catalysts. Thus, a higher Ge content upon the post-stabilization of zeolite frameworks is demanded to reach high metal loadings. Up to now, UTL and *CTH have been the only examples of extra-large pore germanosilicate zeolites used for the incorporation of Ti and Sn, whereas no reported results of Zr-containing extra-large pore zeolites or a general method for M(IV) incorporation are available so far.

It is worth mentioning that direct hydrothermal synthesis of M(IV)-substituted zeolites, as a natural alternative to the post-synthesis approach, is complicated due to the unfavorable crystallization kinetics [7, 35–37], especially for Sn and Zr with large ionic radii [38]. In contrast, post-synthesis isomorphous substitution through the degermanation-metalation process is more flexible and achievable [1, 21]. Meanwhile, the use of costly Ge as the core element in a multi-step post-synthesis method is not an obstacle. Recently, we showed that Ge extracted from the parent zeolite can be recovered and reutilized for cyclic synthesis, effectively reducing the cost of catalyst preparation [28].

Using simultaneous degermanation and metal incorporation, trivalent metals, including Al, Ga, and B [39,40], have been incorporated into the frameworks of germanosilicate zeolites, providing catalysts with the highest concentration of active metal sites reported for respective topologies. However, incorporation of tetravalent elements in germanosilicates, particularly in extra-large pore zeolites, remains challenging due to: i) the hydrolytic instability of germanosilicate zeolites, leading to the structural transformation of the zeolite framework [19,34], and ii) the limitation in the amount of metal loadings due to the preferential formation of metal oxides (SnO₂ and ZrO₂) [11,28].

Taking into account the abovementioned objectives (≥ 14 -ring pores, structure preservation, high concentration of framework M(IV) atoms), we propose a general four-step approach for the design of extra-large pore M(IV)-zeolites:

1) synthesis and 2) post-synthesis stabilization of zeolite frameworks to obtain germanosilicates of targeted topology but unusual chemical composition (Si/Ge ≈ 12);

3) degermanation resulting in the formation of silanol defects – framework vacancies able to accommodate substituting M(IV) element;

4) incorporation of Sn and Zr, resulting in the integration of the respective metals into the zeolite framework and the healing of silanol

defects.

We exemplify the approach with extra-large pore UTL (14×12-rings) and *CTH (14×10-rings) zeolites; however, there are no fundamental limitations in using this method for the whole palette of germanosilicate zeolites. The catalytic activity of these zeolites was confirmed in the MPV reduction of furfural, which served as a model reaction to illustrate the performance of designed zeolites in the valorization of a biomass-derived compound.

2. Experimental part

2.1. Synthesis of structure-directing agents (SDAs)

(6 R,10 S)-6,10-dimethyl-5-azoniaspiro[4.5]decane hydroxide (DMAD), 1,2-dimethyl-3-(3-methylbenzyl)imidazolium hydroxide (DMBI) were synthesized according to Ref. [41,42]. ¹H NMR was used for the confirmation of the SDA structure after dissolution in deuterium oxide. The halogenide form of SDAs was ion-exchanged into hydroxide form using an anionic exchange resin (OH-type of Ambersep® 900, Alfa Aesar). Subsequently, the excess of water in the SDA solution was evaporated at pressure $p = 35$ Torr and temperature $T = 35$ °C until the concentration of ~ 1.0 M.

2.2. Hydrothermal synthesis

UTL zeolite was prepared using DMAD as reported in Ref. [41] The composition of the reaction mixture was 0.96 SiO₂: 0.24 GeO₂: 0.65 DMAD: 30 H₂O. First, 2.28 g of GeO₂ (99.99%, Sigma Aldrich) was dissolved in 54 ml of 1.1 M DMAD solution at 25 °C under magnetic stirring at 400 rpm; then 5.2 g of fumed silica Cab-O-Sil M5 (Thermo Scientific) was introduced into the reaction mixture, which was stirred for another 30 min. Subsequently, the reaction mixture was charged into a 90 ml Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave and heated at 175 °C for ≈ 7 days under agitation (60 rpm).

*CTH zeolite was prepared as reported in Ref. [42] using DMBI as SDA. Typically, 3.5 g of GeO₂ (99.99%, Sigma Aldrich) was dissolved in 64 ml of 1.3 M SDA solution at 25 °C under mechanical stirring at 400 rpm; it was followed by the addition of 28.3 g of tetraethylorthosilicate (TEOS, 98%, Sigma Aldrich). Subsequently, the reaction mixture was stirred for 2 days to hydrolyze TEOS and evaporate ethanol and excess water. 3 ml of HF (48 wt% in water, $\geq 99.99\%$, Sigma Aldrich) was added dropwise with additional manual stirring with spatula for 10 min. The resulting reaction mixture with a molar composition of 0.8 SiO₂: 0.2 GeO₂: 0.5 DMBI: 0.5 HF: 10 H₂O was charged into a 90 ml Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave and heated at 160 °C under static conditions for 30 days.

Solid products were collected by filtration, washed sequentially with 300 ml of deionized water and 100 ml of ethanol, and dried at 60 °C overnight. Further calcination was carried out in the oven at 550 °C (UTL) or 580 °C (*CTH) in the 100 ml/min compressed air stream (Linde) for 6 h at a heating rate of 2 °C•min⁻¹.

*BEA-micro and *BEA-nano samples with micro- and nanosized crystals, respectively, were prepared according to the method described in Ref. [43] with some modifications. The molar composition of the reaction mixture was 1 SiO₂: 0.04 Al₂O₃: 0.6 TEOH: 0.2 HCl: y H₂O ($y = 5.5$ for *BEA-nano or 20 for *BEA-micro). 11.3 g of tetraethylammonium hydroxide solution (35 wt%, Thermo Scientific Chemicals) and 2.3 g of HCl (14 wt%, Sigma-Aldrich) were added to 6.8 g of distilled water. Then 2.6 g of Aerosil A-175 from Evonik Degussa AG (for *BEA-micro) or A-300 (*BEA-nano) was added under vigorous stirring. After stirring for 30 min, 0.27 g of aluminium hydroxide (Acros Organics) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 60 min. In the case of *BEA-nano, the obtained reaction mixture was dried at 75 °C to the H₂O/SiO₂ molar ratio in the mixture 5.5. The reaction mixture was then placed in a 15 ml Teflon-lined stainless-steel autoclave and subjected to hydrothermal treatment at 140 °C for 7 days under static

conditions. The product was then centrifuged and washed with 100 ml of distilled water until the pH of the filtrate was below 8, dried in an oven at 60 °C, and calcined in a furnace at 600 °C with a temperature rate of 2 °C/min and with a heating time of 6 h.

2.3. Post-synthesis stabilization of germanosilicate zeolites

UTL stabilization. 0.3 g of calcined UTL zeolites were mixed with 30 ml of 1.25 M HCl ethanol solution (ThermoFischer). Then, TEOS (98%, Sigma Aldrich) was introduced into the mixture (1 mmol TEOS/g zeolite) [30,31] with further stirring for 30 min, and then the mixture was charged into the 90 ml Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave and treated at 175 °C for 24 h under static conditions. The solid was isolated by filtration, washed with 100 ml of anhydrous ethanol (>99.8%, VWR Chemicals) with portions of 20 ml and dried at 60 °C. This treatment procedure was repeated 2 times.

***CTH stabilization.** 0.3 g of calcined *CTH zeolites were mixed with 30 ml of 6 M HCl, the mixture was loaded into the Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave and treated at 100 °C for 10 h under static conditions [31]. Solid samples were recovered by filtration, washed with 100 ml of anhydrous ethanol (>99.8%, VWR Chemicals) with portions of 20 ml, and dried at 60 °C.

As-stabilized UTL and *CTH zeolites were calcined in the oven at 550 °C for 6 h at a heating rate of 1 °C·min⁻¹ without gas flow. The final stabilized sample was denoted as Zeolite(S).

2.4. Degermanation followed by metal incorporation

The degermanation of the UTL(S) and *CTH(S) samples was achieved by the treatment with distilled water (the liquid-to-solid ratio is 100 ml/g) three times at 25 °C for 1 h. The obtained samples were denoted as Zeolite(S)-hydro.

Tin chloride (IV) (1 M solution in heptane, Sigma-Aldrich) and zirconium chloride (IV) powder (≥ 99.5%, Sigma-Aldrich) were used as sources of Sn and Zr, respectively.

The Sn-zeolites were prepared by the wet impregnation method [28, 44]. The degermanated zeolites were first heated at 450 °C for 4 h with 1 °C·min⁻¹ temperature ramp to remove adsorbed water. The activated zeolites were treated with 0.45 M of SnCl₄ in heptane (solid/liquid ratio of 20 g/l) at 95 °C for 4 days in nitrogen atmosphere. The solid products were recovered by filtration and washed sequentially with heptane (>99%, ThermoScientific) and anhydrous methanol (VWR Chemicals) to ensure the removal of all unreacted metal precursors (solid/liquid ratios of 20 g/l). Further calcination at 450 °C for 4 h with temperature ramp of 1 °C·min⁻¹ allowed obtaining Sn-zeolites, named Zeolite/Sn.

Zr-zeolites were prepared using the vapor-state ion-exchange

method [45]. The synthesis was carried out in a self-sealing quartz crucible (Fisherbrand, 7/8 in.OD) as shown in Scheme 1. Firstly, degermanated zeolites (0.25 g) were placed in the quartz cap of the crucible and activated at 450 °C and for 4 h with a temperature ramp of 1 °C·min⁻¹ to remove adsorbed water. After the temperature decreased to 250 °C, the quartz tube with anhydrous ZrCl₄ powder (0.5 g) was placed in the oven. The zeolite sample and metal precursor were separated with a thermally stable borosilicate glass filter (P-LAB), which can withstand a high temperature of up to 500 °C. The vapor-phase treatment took place at 300 °C for 10 h with a heating rate of 1 °C·min⁻¹. Finally, the filter and quartz tube were removed from the oven and the samples were further calcined at 550 °C for 6 h with a temperature ramp of 1 °C·min⁻¹ to ensure completeness of metal incorporation. The samples were designated as Zeolite/Zr.

2.5. Dealumination and post-synthesis incorporation of metals into dealuminated *BEA zeolite

Dealumination of commercial *BEA-com. (Zeolyst, CP-814E), *BEA-nano and *BEA-micro zeolites was carried out by the treatment with 13 M HNO₃ (VWR Chemicals) at 80 °C for 4 h (solid/liquid ratio 20 ml/g) according to Ref. [46]. Incorporation of Zr and Sn in the dealuminated *BEA zeolites was performed as described in Section 2.4. The dealuminated *BEA samples were designated as *BEA-deAl-com, *BEA-deAl-nano, and *BEA-deAl-micro. The respective Sn- and Zr-substituted *BEA zeolites were named as *BEA/Me-com., *BEA/Me-nano, and *BEA/Me-micro, where Me is Sn or Zr.

2.6. Characterization techniques

Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) was used to examine the crystallinity of zeolite samples through Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.154$ nm), which was performed on a Bruker AXS-D8 Advance diffractometer equipped with a LYNXEYE XE-T detector in the Bragg-Brentano geometry. Prior to measurement, samples were gently ground and carefully loaded into the holder.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (FEI Quanta 200 F microscope) was used to assess the crystal morphology of zeolite, and equipped Energy-dispersive X-ray analysis (EDX) was used to determine the contents of Si, Ge, Al, Sn, and Zr in zeolite.

UV-vis spectra were recorded on a Cary 300 ultraviolet-visible (UV-vis) spectrophotometer in the wavelength range of 190 ~ 600 nm. Before the measurement of UV-vis spectra, the zeolite catalysts were activated at 450 °C for 2 h with a temperature ramp of 5 °C/min to exclude the influence of water adsorption on the observed spectral features, previously reported in Ref. [47]. BaSO₄ was used as a reference.

N₂ and Ar sorption analyses were performed on a static volumetric apparatus 3Flex (Micromeritics) at -196 °C and -186 °C, respectively. Before measurements, the zeolites were activated at 250 °C for 8 h under vacuum with a turbo molecular pump. The BET method was applied to calculate the specific surface area in the relative pressure range (p/p_0) of 0.05 ~ 0.20 [48]. The micropore volume (V_{micro}) [49] was evaluated using the t-plot method. The mesopore volume (V_{meso}) was calculated using the BJH algorithm [50] from the desorption branch of the isotherms. The pore size distribution (PSD) was calculated from argon isotherms using the NLDFT model (Ar on oxides at 87 K).

Fourier infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy measurements were performed on a Nicolet iS50 spectrometer with a transmission MCT/B detector; all spectra were collected at 25 °C by 128 scans with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹. Further experimental details on determining the acid site concentration and strength are given in the Supporting Information.

2.7. Catalytic tests

MPV reduction of furfural with isopropanol was used to study the

Scheme 1. Quartz crucible used for incorporation of Zr into zeolites. The excess of ZrCl₄ was used to mitigate the influence of water traces, which may be present in the treatment crucible and result in the formation of non-volatile ZrOCl₂.

catalytic performance of Sn- and Zr-containing Lewis acid zeolite catalysts. The catalytic experiments were performed in a 25-ml glass batch reactor using a multi-experiment workstation StarFish or in a microflow unit Microactivity Effi (PID Eng&Tech - Micromeritics).

For batch catalytic experiments, the catalysts were activated at 450 °C for 4 h. Then 0.2 g of catalyst and n-dodecane (0.1 g, internal standard) were added to 6 ml of isopropanol in a three-neck flask equipped with a thermometer and a condenser and sealed with a rubber septum. The reaction mixture was heated to 80 °C and the reaction started by adding 1 mmol of furfural. Samples of the reaction mixture (0.1 ml) were collected periodically with a 1 ml PP/PE syringe (Sigma Aldrich). The probes were centrifuged to separate the catalyst and analyzed using a gas chromatograph (GC, Agilent 7890B) equipped with HP-5 column (length: 30 m, diameter: 0.32 mm, film: 0.25 μm), FID detector, and autosampler. Reaction products were determined using a Thermo Scientific® ISQ LT - TRACE 1310 GC/MS.

Continuous MPV reduction of furfural was performed in a stainless-steel reactor with an internal diameter of 5.1 mm and a length of 287 mm. To avoid a high pressure drop on the reactor, the catalyst (300 mg) was granulated and sieved to a fraction between 200 and 500 μm and diluted with silicon carbide inert (300 mg, size fraction of 500 μm). Prior to reaction, the catalysts were activated in situ at 450 °C for 4 h with a synthetic air flow of 100 ml/min. Subsequently, the reactor was cooled, fled with pure isopropanol, and the reaction was carried out at 70 °C using a reaction mixture with a molar ratio of isopropanol/furfural/n-dodecane of 78/1/0.58 (the same as batch reactor) at a flow rate of 0.31 ml/min (WHSV=50 h⁻¹, reaction mixture delivered by an HPLC pump). Periodic samples of the reaction solution were collected through a sampling valve positioned downstream of the reactor, and subsequently analyzed offline using a gas chromatography (GC, Agilent 8860) equipped with HP-5 column (length: 30 m, diameter: 0.32 mm, film: 0.25 μm), FID detector, and autosampler.

For the quantitative treatment of the kinetic data, the internal standard calibration method was applied using the following commercially available compounds supplied by Sigma Aldrich: furfural (99%), furfuryl alcohol (98%), propyl levulinate (>95%), α-angelica lactone (98%), γ-valerolactone (GVL, 99%), n-dodecane (>99%). The amount of commercially unavailable isopropyl furfuryl ether was estimated using the effective carbon number concept [51].

The conversion of a reactant (X), product yield (Y), and selectivity of a particular product at a certain conversion (S) and mass balance after 24 h in batch experiments were calculated from the following equations:

$$X = \frac{n(\text{furfural})_0 - n(\text{furfural})_\tau}{n(\text{furfural})_0} \cdot 100 \%$$

$$Y = \frac{n(\text{product})_\tau}{n(\text{furfural})_0} \cdot 100 \%$$

$$S = \frac{Y}{X} \cdot 100 \% = \frac{n(\text{product})_\tau}{n(\text{furfural})_0 - n(\text{furfural})_\tau} \cdot 100 \%$$

$$\text{Mass balance} = \frac{\sum n(\text{product})_{24\text{h}} + n(\text{furfural})_{24\text{h}}}{n(\text{furfural})_0} \cdot 100 \%$$

where $n(\text{furfural})_0$ and $n(\text{furfural})_\tau$ are amounts of reactant in reaction mixture at initial time and after specified time τ , respectively; $n(\text{product})_\tau$ is an amount of a product formed in reaction mixture after specified time τ ; $\sum n(\text{product})_{24\text{h}}$ is the amounts of products identified in the reaction mixture after 24 hours.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis

The targeted extra-large pore Sn- and Zr-zeolites UTL and *CTH were

prepared via a four-step approach by combining the direct- and post-synthesis steps (Scheme 2), which include the consecutive formation of the following materials:

- (1) Ge-rich zeolites designated with standard IZA codes (UTL and *CTH);
- (2) Ge-poor (stabilized) zeolites obtained as a result of partial substitution of Ge atoms with Si, and designated as UTL(S) and *CTH(S);
- (3) Deficient roughly siliceous UTL(S)-hydro and *CTH(S)-hydro materials obtained by the removal of most of the remaining Ge atoms by hydrolysis;
- (4) Sn- or Zr-zeolites UTL/Sn(Zr), *CTH/Sn(Zr) obtained by incorporation of Sn or Zr atoms into UTL(S)-hydro and *CTH(S)-hydro materials.

Thus, the complete sequence of transformations can be represented as Zeolite→Zeolite(S)→Zeolite(S)-hydro→Zeolite/Sn(Zr), where Zeolite is either UTL or *CTH. To trace the evolution of zeolite frameworks and to rationalize the catalytic behaviour of final metal-substituted zeolites, we analyzed the structural and textural properties of materials (2) – (4) formed in the intermediate stages. The parameters for comparison were structural order (according to the PXRD data), porosity (V_{micro} , V_{meso} , and S_{BET}), chemical composition (Si/Ge or Si/Sn(Zr)), and crystal morphology (SEM data).

The PXRD patterns of all Ge-rich samples (Figure S1) are consistent with the reported data, thus confirming the phase purity and high crystallinity of each zeolite [42,52,53]. Ge-for-Si substitution, hydrolysis and subsequent metal incorporation do not cause significant structural changes, as the diffraction peaks in the PXRD patterns of the stabilized, deficient, and final samples maintained their positions (Figure S1). The variation in the relative intensities of the diffraction lines, especially pronounced for the UTL→UTL(S)→UTL(S)-hydro→UTL/Sn(Zr) sequence of transformations, may be related to the change in chemical composition (Table 1) and thus the change in the relative population of the specific framework positions. In the case of *CTH, degermanation leading to non-compensated removal of framework elements (Ge) results in notable decrease of relative intensity of the diffraction peak around 7 degree, which is restored after following metallation (Figure S1b). EDX analysis revealed a gradual increase in the Si/Ge ratio after stabilization (from 4 – 5 to 12) and subsequent hydrolysis steps (from 12 to 30 – 34), which corresponds to the progressive removal of Ge framework atoms accompanied by Si insertion. The following metallation provides metal-substituted zeolites (Si/Sn = 40 – 51, Si/Zr = 14 – 15) for both the UTL and *CTH frameworks.

In addition to structural maintenance and chemical changes throughout different synthesis steps, we have addressed whether diffusion-related samples' features, such as porosity and crystal morphology, are affected during proposed modifications. The initial UTL and *CTH materials show type-I nitrogen physisorption isotherms characteristic of microporous materials (Figure S2). Non-equivalent substitution of Ge for Si in the first modification step (stabilization) causes the formation of additional mesopores (V_{meso} up to 0.13 cm³·g⁻¹) reflected in the apparent change in the shape of the isotherms (Figure S2), which remains practically the same throughout the hydrolysis and metal incorporation steps. In addition, stabilization via Ge-for-Si substitution resulted in a decrease in the zeolite density, and hence, an increase in the micropore volume. In combination with the development of mesopores, this caused a slight increase in the BET area (470→534 m²·g⁻¹ for UTL and 360→402 m²·g⁻¹ for *CTH). The generation of defects upon hydrolysis expectedly resulted in a decrease in the textural characteristics (both V_{micro} and S_{BET}), which were restored after healing defects upon incorporation of Sn atoms (Table 1). Thus, from the formal point of view, the microporosity in such structures remains nearly unchanged during the multi-step synthesis process, as it can be seen from the pore-size distribution curves (Figure S3). The average pore sizes maxima reflect the structure of the individual materials studied, being in the range of 7.8–8.6 Å for UTL zeolites and 7.2–7.6 Å for *CTH zeolites. In the case of Zr incorporation, the evolution of the micropores

Scheme 2. The protocol for target synthesis of Sn- and Zr-substituted extra-large pore UTL and *CTH zeolites.

Table 1

Chemical composition, textural and acidic properties of zeolite catalysts under study.

Sample	Textural properties		Acidic properties, $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$			Chemical composition		
	$V_{\text{micro}}, \text{cm}^3\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$	$V_{\text{meso}}, \text{cm}^3\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$	$S_{\text{BET}}, \text{m}^2\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$	C_L	C_B	C_{Σ}	Si/Me	$C_{\text{Me}}, \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$
UTL-4	0.20	0.03	470	na ^e	na	na	5 ^a	na
UTL(S)	0.22	0.13	534	na	na	na	12 ^a	na
UTL(S)-hydro	0.18	0.11	459	na	na	na	30 ^a	na
UTL/Sn	0.19	0.11	478	210	0	210	51 ^b	310
UTL/Zr	0.16	0.09	384	586	0	586	15 ^c	978
*CTH-4	0.15	0.05	360	na	na	na	4 ^a	na
*CTH (S)	0.15	0.08	402	na	na	na	12 ^a	na
*CTH(S)-hydro	0.15	0.05	371	na	na	na	34 ^a	na
*CTH/Sn	0.16	0.08	421	183	0	183	40 ^b	390
*CTH/Zr	0.11	0.05	277	474	0	474	14 ^c	1040
*BEA-com.	0.16	0.60	558	320	310	630	10 ^d	na
*BEA-deAl-com.	0.18	0.58	600	na	na	na	>1000 ^d	na
*BEA/Sn-com.	0.15	0.49	500	280	0	230	30 ^b	513
*BEA/Zr-com.	0.16	0.42	540	240	0	310	28 ^c	560
*BEA-micro	0.16	0.18	420	300	300	600	12 ^d	na
*BEA-deAl-micro	na	na	Na	na	na	na	>1000 ^d	na
*BEA/Sn-micro	0.14	0.12	430	290	0	290	27 ^b	570
*BEA-nano	0.18	0.75	640	300	300	600	12 ^d	na
*BEA-deAl-nano	na	na	Na	na	na	na	>1000 ^d	na
*BEA/Sn-nano	0.18	0.81	650	310	0	310	22 ^b	670

^a Me=Ge,

^b Me=Sn,

^c Me=Zr,

^d Me=Al.

^e na – not analyzed

resulted in a noticeable decrease in V_{micro} and S_{BET} (Table 1), as also seen from PSD curves becoming broader and lowered in intensities, especially pronounced for *CTH. The deterioration of the textural parameters in the case of Zr incorporation may be related to the formation of oligomeric oxide species that partially block the space in the pores. Although there were no signs of separate oxide phase in XRD (Figure S1), SEM images revealed the presence of extra-phase, most probably ZrO_2 on the surface of the zeolite crystals (bright particles in Fig. 1). Thus, the formation of sub-nm oxide particles cannot be excluded that potentially can influence acid and catalytic properties discussed in the following

sections. The SEM images of UTL-4 showed uniform thin rectangular $80 \times 50 \times 2 \mu\text{m}$ -sized zeolite crystals (Fig. 1). Similar morphology, but smaller crystal sizes ($6 \times 2 \times 0.2 \mu\text{m}$) was observed in *CTH-4 zeolite. When comparing the parent materials with the final products (Fig. 1), only minor changes in morphology can be found. The consistency observed in the SEM images of the parent and treated samples underscores the stability of the material structures throughout the synthesis processes.

In addition to the extra-large pore Sn- and Zr-UTL and *CTH zeolites, the reference zeolite catalysts have been prepared by dealumination,

Fig. 1. SEM images of the zeolites under study (initial UTL, *CTH, *BEA-com., and their derivatives UTL/Sn, *CTH/Sn, *BEA/Sn-com, UTL/Zr, *CTH/Zr, *BEA/Zr-com). Sn-substituted *BEA zeolites *BEA/Sn-nano and *BEA/Sn-micro with nano- and micron-size crystal dimensions, respectively, are shown in the bottom panel.

followed by incorporation of Sn (or Zr) into commercial aluminosilicate zeolite *BEA-com and *BEA samples specially designed with variable crystal sizes, *BEA-micro and *BEA-nano (Table 1). XRD patterns (Figure S1), nitrogen physisorption results (Figure S2, Table 1), and PSD analysis (Figure S3) revealed the preservation of the structure ordering and porous architecture of *BEA zeolites upon the post-synthesis isomorphous substitution. At the same time, the results of the

chemical analysis evidenced the leaching of the most Al atoms ($\text{Si}/\text{Al} > 1000$) and the incorporation of Sn ($\text{Si}/\text{Sn} = 22 - 30$) or Zr ($\text{Si}/\text{Zr} = 28$) under the applied conditions. Due to the small size, it was difficult to estimate the exact crystal dimensions for commercial *BEA-com samples (Fig. 1). At the same time, the particles of the *BEA/Sn-nano and *BEA/Sn-micro samples additionally synthesized for the purpose of catalytic assessment (see section “Catalytic performance of Sn- and Zr-zeolites”

Fig. 2. UV-vis spectra of Zeolite/Sn (a) and Zeolite/Zr (b): UTL (red lines), *CTH (blue lines), *BEA-com. (black lines) zeolites.

for details) were characterized by relatively uniform size at the nano-scale (200 nm spheres) or micron-scale range (irregular-shape 5 – 20 μm species).

3.2. Acidic properties of Sn- and Zr-zeolites

UV–vis spectra of the activated Sn- and Zr-zeolites (Fig. 2) revealed a strong absorption band at approx. 225 and 205 nm, respectively, which is indicative of ligand-to-metal charge transitions for tetrahedrally coordinated T^{IV} species [54–56]. In the case of Sn, the presence of a fraction of metal atoms at extra-framework positions is revealed by the shoulder band at ca. 255 nm, while for Zr, no bands related to the bulk ZrO_2 crystallites (triple bands at 207, 214 and 227 nm [57]) were found in the spectra of substituted zeolites. However, both tetrahedrally coordinated framework Zr species and ZrOCl_2 typically show a dominant band at ca. 205 nm [58].

Therefore, a comprehensive analysis of acid properties was conducted through FTIR spectroscopy, to draw conclusions about the state of the metals and their concentration within zeolite frameworks, which is essential for establishing a correlation with the catalytic performance. Strong Lewis acidity in Al- and Sn-zeolites is generally analyzed by FTIR spectroscopy of adsorbed pyridine according to the following steps: (i) pyridine adsorption on acid sites at $T = 150 \sim 200$ °C followed by desorption at the same temperature; and (ii) evaluation of the intensity of $\nu_{19\text{b}}$ band of pyridine adsorbed on LAS ($\nu_{19\text{b}}\text{-LAS } 1450 \sim 1455 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) [59] by using the Beer-Lambert law and the reported molar absorption coefficients [47]. In contrast to zeolites with strong acid sites, the $\nu_{19\text{b}}$ band of pyridine adsorbed on weaker Zr-associated Lewis acid sites [60, 61] overlaps with that of H-bonded pyridine ($\nu_{19\text{b}}\text{-H } 1443 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (Figure S4). Therefore, the application of $\nu_{19\text{b}}$ band for the analysis of the number of LAS in Zr-zeolites is limited, and it was also recently reported for weakly acidic Ti-zeolites [62].

Therefore, an alternative approach based on the evaluation of the intensity of $\nu_{8\text{a}}\text{-LAS}$ band at 1608 cm^{-1} was developed to quantify LAS in Zr-zeolites after saturation with pyridine. During pyridine adsorption, only $\nu_{8\text{a}}\text{-LAS}$ was observed upon the introduction of the first doses of the probe molecule, while the $\nu_{8\text{a}}\text{-H}$ band appeared at 1596 cm^{-1} when adding more pyridine (Figure S4a). Therefore, the proposed approach allows eliminating the contribution of the H-bonded probe molecule by

controlling the concentration of the introduced pyridine ($< 2.5 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, Figure S4b), and ultimately determining the molar absorption coefficient (ϵ (Zr-LAS) = $0.73 \text{ cm}^2/\mu\text{mol}$) by correlating the band area of $\nu_{8\text{a}}\text{-LAS}$ at 1608 cm^{-1} with the amount of adsorbed probe molecule (Figure S4c).

Once confirming the value of ϵ (LAS), the adsorption of an excess of pyridine (~ 3.5 Torr) followed by the thermo-desorption at 50, 75, 100, 120, 150, 200 °C allowed us to calculate the concentration and strength of LAS in Sn- (details are shown in the supporting information) and Zr-zeolites using the $\nu_{8\text{a}}$ band centered at 1608 cm^{-1} (Figure S5). According to the pyridine thermodesorption results (Fig. 3), the acid strength for the Sn-sites was slightly higher compared to the Zr-sites, which is consistent with the published results [60,63]. Generally, a lower concentration of Sn- and Zr-associated acid sites determined by FTIR of adsorbed pyridine was observed in comparison to the EDX results (Table 1), revealing the presence of extra-framework Sn/Zr-species in all zeolites under study. This phenomenon is more pronounced for Zr-samples, being in line with the physisorption results (Table 1) and the microscopy observation (Fig. 1 and related discussion).

4. Catalytic performance of Sn- and Zr-zeolites

MPV reduction of furfural (Scheme 3) to furfuryl alcohol over Lewis acid sites can be accompanied by further cross-etherification of furfuryl alcohol with alcohol used as a solvent/reactant for MPV reduction. The latter reaction proceeds over Lewis or Brønsted acid sites and generates furfuryl ethers. In bi-functional systems containing both Lewis and Brønsted acid centers, furfuryl ethers can undergo further transformation to alkyl levulinates, unsaturated α -, β -lactones or saturated γ -valerolactone (GVL).

Figure S6 shows the furfural conversion profiles versus time for different Sn- and Zr-zeolite catalysts studied in the batch reactor. After reacting for 2 h, $\sim 95\%$ furfural conversion was achieved over both Sn- and Zr-UTL zeolites, which is much higher than those of the respective *CTH zeolites ($< 30\%$). Considering similar concentrations of Lewis acid sites in the respective Sn- and Zr-UTL and *CTH zeolites (Fig. 3), the difference in their catalytic performance can be related to either (1) the differences in crystal sizes that could affect the internal diffusion of the reactants to the catalyst active sites or 2) the differences in pore topology

Fig. 3. Concentration of acid sites (in mmol/g) in T^{IV} -substituted UTL, *CTH, and *BEA zeolites that retain adsorbed pyridine at variable temperatures according to the legend. x% refers to the fraction of acid sites that retain adsorbed pyridine after desorption at 200 °C.

Scheme 3. MPV reduction of furfural to furfuryl alcohol and its subsequent transformation, leading to different products over zeolite catalysts.

that affects the formation of the transition state for MPV reduction. To verify assumption (1), two reference Sn-zeolite catalysts, *BEA-Sn-nano and *BEA-Sn-micro with similar concentrations of acid sites and textural characteristics (Table 1), but different crystal sizes (Fig. 1) were compared in furfural transformation under the same experimental conditions. A quite similar conversion vs. time profile observed for *BEA-Sn-nano and *BEA-Sn-micro (Figure S7) ruled out the effect of the catalyst crystal size on the furfural conversion under the experimental conditions. On the other hand, considering the molecular size of the transition state in the MPV reduction of furfural at 6.6 Å [64] and the pore sizes of *CTH and UTL zeolites, it can be expected that only 14-ring pores (9.1×7.2 Å) but not 10-ring channels (6.2×4.5 Å) in the *CTH catalyst can be suitable for the formation of this transition state. In contrast, UTL contains intersected 14- (9.5×7.1 Å) and 12-ring pores (8.5×5.5 Å), being large enough for the accommodation of the targeted transition state and providing high furfural conversion.

Furthermore, the different nature of the acid sites has an apparent impact on the distribution of products achieved over UTL/Sn (main product – furfuryl ether, 42% yield) and UTL/Zr (main product – furfuryl alcohol, 63% yield, Table 2). Weaker acid sites in UTL/Zr zeolite do not prevent sufficiently fast desorption of the formed furfuryl alcohol, while the higher acid strength in Sn-zeolite may cause stronger adsorption of the targeted product and thus increase the probability of its further transformation to furfuryl ether and other secondary products. The same trend of increasing the yield of furfuryl ether over Sn- vs. Zr-zeolite catalysts was observed for the *CTH and *BEA-com samples.

Notably, the reference Sn-substituted large-pore *BEA zeolite catalysts with a 3-dimensional system of intersecting 12-ring channels (6.6×6.7 and 5.6×5.6 Å) showed comparable yields of furfuryl ether (44 – 62% after 24 h, Table 2) as the extra-large UTL/Sn zeolite (51% after 24 h). On the other hand, the worse mass balance observed for the MPV

reduction of furfural over *BEA/Sn zeolites (73 – 91%) compared to that of UTL/Sn (91 – 94%) may suggest more facile deposition of some of the furfural transformation products in the pore system of *BEA with potential negative influence on the durability of this zeolite catalyst.

The catalytic behavior of UTL/Sn and *BEA-/Sn-com in the MPV reduction of furfural was further tested under flow conditions. Within the duration of the catalytic experiment (210 min), UTL/Sn and *BEA/Sn-com. exhibited a similar dependence of conversion over time on stream (TOS, Fig. 4a). In terms of selectivity, unlike in batch reactor, only a negligible quantity of isopropyl furfuryl ether was detected for both Sn-zeolites. The absence of this side product can be attributed to the relatively short contact time of the generated products with the catalyst bed (WHSV = 50 h^{-1}) in the flow system, which prevents a secondary transformation of the furfuryl alcohol to isopropyl furfuryl ether and further (Scheme 2). Instead, furfural diisopropylacetal (hereafter *acetal*, a product of a reversible reaction between furfural and isopropyl alcohol, Scheme 2) was formed. Acetal was not observed in the batch experiments at high furfural conversions due to its decomposition; however, it was detected in the reaction mixture at the early stages of the batch reactions.

*BEA/Sn-com. was more selective towards the furfuryl alcohol than the UTL/Sn in the initial period of the reaction (TOS < 90 min), but it quickly dropped to the same level observed for the UTL/Sn from the beginning of the experiment (Fig. 4). In general, utilization of both catalysts in the flow mode allows one to minimize the yields of irreversibly formed undesired products (ethers, esters, and lactones) due to the minimization of the residence time hindering the transformation of primarily generated furfuryl alcohol.

Table 2

Catalytic performance of Sn- and Zr-zeolite catalysts in the MPV reduction of furfural in a batch reactor.

	T ^{IV} Metal	Conversion of furfural (%)	Yield of product (%)					Mass balance (%)
			furfuryl alcohol	Isopropyl furfuryl ether	Isopropyl levulinate	β-lactones	GVL	
UTL	Sn	100 (100)	31 (16)	42 (51)	13 (19)	2 (3)	1 (2)	91
	Zr	100 (100)	63 (52)	23 (31)	5 (7)	1 (2)	1 (2)	94
*CTH	Sn	31 (42)	20 (24)	6 (11)	<1 (2)	<1 (1)	n.d. (n.d.)	93
	Zr	71 (82)	50 (76)	1 (2)	n.d. (1)	n.d. (n.d.)	n.d. (n.d.)	98
*BEA-com.	Sn	100 (100)	3 (0)	74(62)	4 (6)	4 (5)	n.d. (n.d.)	73
	Zr	64 (84)	27(19)	24 (52)	0 (2)	2 (4)	n.d. (n.d.)	91
*BEA-nano	Sn	84 (96)	3 (2)	58 (66)	3 (4)	9 (11)	n.d. (n.d.)	86
*BEA-micro	Sn	96 (100)	1 (0)	57 (44)	6 (13)	15 (34)	n.d. (n.d.)	91
Blank	no	<1	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.

Reaction conditions: 80 °C, 6 h (24 h)

Fig. 4. Conversion of furfural (a) and yield of furfuryl alcohol versus time on stream in MPV reduction over *BEA/Sn-com. (black lines) and UTL/Sn (red lines).

5. Conclusions

The successful synthesis of stannio/zirconosilicate UTL and *CTH extra-large pore zeolites was accomplished through a multi-step approach by combining the advantages of direct- and post-synthesis methods. Despite its formal complexity, the proposed method is experimentally simple, easily scalable, and allows faster access to M(IV)-containing extra-large pore zeolites compared to the direct synthesis. Integration of tetravalent elements into zeolite frameworks was confirmed by using a combination of spectroscopic methods, while diffraction analysis validated the phase purity and high crystallinity of the prepared zeolite catalysts. Using the proposed method, Sn- and Zr-zeolites UTL and *CTH with Si/Sn = 40 – 51 and Si/Zr = 14 – 15 were achieved, although the characterization results of UV-vis and FTIR-Py spectroscopy do not exclude the formation of the extraframework non-acidic Zr and Sn species, most probably ZrO_2 and SnO_2 .

The targeted extra-large pore zeolites UTL and *CTH with variable nature of the Lewis acid sites, Sn or Zr, showed distinct conversions and product distributions in the MPV reduction of furfural under batch and flow conditions. In a batch reactor, UTL/Zr characterized by lower acidity compared to UTL/Sn, demonstrated a notable preference for the production of furfuryl alcohol with a yield of 52% compared to 16% for Sn-substituted analogue. This preference was ascribed to the optimal interaction between the primary emerged product and the Zr active sites at long residence times, which facilitates product release and prevents the generation of additional products through secondary reactions. While showing similar yield of isopropyl furfuryl ether (51% and 44 – 62% after 24 h) as the reference *BEA/Sn zeolite in the batch, the designed extra-large pore UTL/Sn zeolite was characterized by better mass balance (91% for UTL/Sn and 73 – 91% for *BEA/Sn). This result may indicate hindered deposition of certain furfural transformation products within the extra-large pores of UTL/Sn. In line with this observation, UTL/Sn (the yield of furfuryl alcohol 10 – 7% for 210 min TOS) showed more stable performance in MPV reduction of furfural under the flow conditions than *BEA/Sn (41 – 8%). In general, the flow mode allows to minimize the yield of irreversibly formed undesired products (ethers, esters, and lactones) over UTL/Sn and *BEA/Sn catalyst due to the minimization of a residence time hindering the

transformation of initially generated furfuryl alcohol. Further optimization of the flow catalytic run is anticipated to allow for approaching reasonably high yields of the desired product in a flow mode.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mariya V. Shamzhy: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Talat Zakeri:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Qiudi Yue:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Jin Zhang:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Martin Kubu:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Roman Barakov:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Jan Prech:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Maksym Opanasenko:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.cattod.2024.114825.

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